

The Study of Narcissism and it's Correlation with Empathy in Medical Students.

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Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Narcissism characterized by authority, exhibitionism, superiority, entitlement, exploitativeness, manipulative self-sufficiency and vanity has not been studied enough among physicians, let alone medical students. Empathy is important for both diagnosis and patient care. Empathy is important for the physician as well as his patient simply because it is protective against physician burnout.

Aim and Objective: 1. To assess the prevalence of narcissism amongst medical students.

2. To assess the prevalence of empathy amongst medical students.

3. To analyze association between narcissism and empathy amongst medical students.

Materials and Methods: A cross sectional study was conducted by circulating online questionnaire survey among medical students studying in C U Shah Medical College from October 2023 to December 2023, questionnaire was used for narcissism was PNI 52 and for Empathy was QCAE and sociodemographic factors. Association between narcissism and empathy was done using Shapiro-wilk normality testing & Pearson correlation. An informed consent was taken before filling the online form. Total of 112 medical students participated in the study.

Results: In this study prevalence of pathological narcissism was found to be 30.36%. Prevalence of cognitive & affective empathy was found to be 69.64% and 68.75%. There was a weak, negative correlation between Cognitive Empathy and Grandiose Narcissism, which was statistically significant. There was a weak, positive correlation between Affective Empathy and Grandiose Narcissism, which was not statistically significant. There was a weak, negative correlation between Cognitive Empathy and Vulnerable Narcissism, which was statistically significant. There was a weak, negative correlation between Affective Empathy and Vulnerable Narcissism, which was not statistically significant.

Conclusion: According to above results, correlations suggests that individuals with higher cognitive empathy tend to have lower level of narcissistic tendencies and individuals with higher cognitive empathy tend to be less vulnerable. By promoting empathy and addressing narcissistic tendencies, medical professionals can provide better patient care and improve health outcomes.

Keywords: Narcissism, Empathy, Medical Students

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Introduction

Empathy: These definitions could be understood as concepts defined by Stepien and Baernstein (2006) as cognitive empathy (i.e., understanding and identifying patients' perspective), affective (i.e., imagining patients' emotions, and own emotional reactions), although Stepien and Baernstein (2006) also include behavioural (i.e., communicating understanding of the patient perspective to the patient) and moral (i.e., motivation to empathise).

Empathy is an emotional response (affective), dependent upon the interaction between trait capacities and state influences. Empathic processes are automatically elicited but are also shaped by top-down control processes. The resulting emotion is similar to one's perception (directly experienced or imagined) and understanding (cognitive empathy) of the stimulus emotion, with recognition that the source of the emotion is not one's own.

Narcissism: Narcissistic personality disorder (NPD) is a clinical diagnosis included in the DSM-

V (1), described as Grandiose views of the self, an active fantasy life involving personal successes, the assumption that one is unique or special, an arrogant attitude and desire for admiration, a sense of entitlement and envy for others' success and possessions, and little empathy for others and a willingness to exploit them [1].

This personality trait has been identified as an area of interest based on increasing media attention regarding narcissism and its manifestation in the workplace and relationships. Anecdotally, and supported by limited literature, stories are present within healthcare services of problematic behaviour consistent with narcissistic traits including workplace bullying, superiority and domineering conduct. However, this has not been formally researched and therefore requires further investigation.

Narcissists focus on conducting themselves in ways that have benefits for themselves and show little regard for how their actions may impact others, that is, they have a high agentic and low communal focus [2]. High agency refers to often inflated positive self-views, entitlement, and, grandiosity. Narcissisms mainly are pathological and healthy types. Pathological narcissism mainly divided in Grandiose (i.e., Characterized by an exaggerated sense of self-importance, superiority and grandiosity) and Vulnerable (i.e., Characterized by fragile self-esteem, insecurity and hypersensitivity to criticism or rejection) types of narcissism.

Aim and Objective:

1. To assess the prevalence of narcissism amongst medical students.
2. To assess the prevalence of empathy amongst medical students.
3. To analyze association between narcissism and empathy amongst medical students.

Materials and Methodology:

A cross sectional study was conducted by circulating online questionnaire survey(11) among medical students studying in C U Shah Medical College from October 2023 to December 2023, questionnaire was used for narcissism was PNI 52(12) and for Empathy was QCAE(13) and sociodemographic factors. Association between narcissism and empathy was done using Shapiro-wilk normality testing & Pearson correlation. Total of 112 medical students participated in the study. A convenient sampling was done after explaining and taking consent from the medical students and

sample collection was done using an online questionnaire google form among medical students.

PNI – 52 scoring system was used for the assessment of narcissism which is 6 points scale having 52 questions in the system. PNI -52 divided in main 3 categories of narcissism – grandiosity, vulnerability and pathological narcissism. The scoring system is from 0-5 with 0 means not at all like me to 5 means very much like me. Grandiosity and Vulnerability consist of 3 subtypes each having the questions according to the subtype of narcissism. Mean of these subtypes of narcissism suggest the Pathological Narcissism(12).

QCAE (Questionnaire of Cognitive and Affective Empathy) scoring system is used for assessment of empathy among medical students. QCAE consist of total of 31 questions to assess empathy. In this questionnaire certain questions are used to assess Cognitive empathy and certain questions are used to assess Affective empathy(13). Scoring was done from 1-4 in which 1 mean strongly disagree to 4 means strongly agree. Mean of these scoring suggest the average of each type of Empathy.

To assess the correlation between the types of Narcissism and type of Empathy Shapiro-wilk normality testing and Pearson's correlation is used, which is helpful to find out the result whether narcissism and empathy is positively related or negatively related.

The authors assert that all procedures contributing to this work comply with the ethical standards of the relevant national and institutional committees on human experimentation and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2008. This study involving the participants were approved by The Institutional Ethics Committee and Scientific Review Committee – Subcommittee (Human Research) of C. U. Shah Medical College and hospital Surendranagar and approval number CUSMC/IEC(HR)/RP/34/2023/Final Approval/330/2023.

Inclusion Criteria: Interns and PG Students Studying in C U Shah Medical Collage

Exclusion Criteria: Interns and PG students diagnosed as psychiatry illness or on psychiatric medications.

Results:

Mean age of the participants were 24.59 ± 3.31 .

Prevalence of pathological narcissism was found to be 30.36%.

Prevalence of cognitive and affective empathy was found to be 69.64% and 68.75% respectively.

Department	Pathological narcissism	
	Present (%)	Absent (%)
Community Medicine	1 (25%)	3 (75%)
General medicine	11 (32%)	23 (68%)
Obstetrics & Gynaecology	1 (33%)	2 (67%)
Orthopaedic	4 (50%)	4 (50%)
Paediatric	2 (29%)	5 (71%)
Pathology	2 (18%)	9(82%)
Psychiatry	2 (17%)	10(83%)
Radiology	2 (33%)	4 (67%)
Surgery	16 (59%)	11(41%)

Table showing pathological narcissism among various departments. Highest pathological narcissism was found in a surgery department (59%), followed by orthopaedic (50%), Radiology (33%), obstetrics and gynaecology (33%), medicine (32%), paediatrics (29%) and community medicine department (25%). Least pathological narcissism was found in psychiatry (17%) and pathology department (18%).

Department	Cognitive Empathy	
	Present	Absent
Community Medicine	3(75%)	1(25%)
General medicine	26(76%)	8(24%)
Obstetrics & Gynaecology	1(33%)	2(67%)
Orthopaedic	6(75%)	2(25%)
Paediatric	5(71%)	2(29%)
Pathology	7(63%)	4(37%)
Psychiatry	9(75%)	3(25%)
Radiology	2(33%)	4(67%)
Surgery	17(62%)	10(38%)

Table showing Cognitive Empathy among various departments. Around 75% Cognitive Empathy was seen in the General medicine, Orthopaedic, Paediatric, Community Medicine and Psychiatry department. Cognitive empathy was 63% and 62% respectively in a pathology and surgery department. Least Cognitive empathy was noted in obstetrics and gynaecology department (33%).

Department	Affective Empathy	
	Present	Absent
Community Medicine	3(75%)	1(25%)
General medicine	25(73%)	9(27%)
Obstetrics & Gynaecology	2(66%)	1(34%)
Orthopaedic	6(75%)	2(25%)
Paediatric	5(71%)	2(29%)
Pathology	7(63%)	4(37%)
Psychiatry	7(58%)	5(42%)
Radiology	4(66%)	2(34%)
Surgery	17(62%)	10(38%)

Table showing Affective Empathy among various departments. Nearly 3/4th percentage Affective Empathy was seen in Community Medicine, General Medicine, Orthopaedic and Paediatric department. Nearly 2/3rd percentage Affective Empathy was seen in obstetrics and gynaecology, Pathology, Radiology and Surgery department. Affective Empathy was least in psychiatry department compare to the all departments.

Tests of Normality	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Cognitive	0.977	112	0.051
Affective	0.986	112	0.321
Grandiosity	0.993	112	0.848
Pathological narcissism	0.991	112	0.673
Vulnerability	0.992	112	0.768

As per Shapiro-wilk normality testing data were following normal distribution(9). So parametric measure of tests was used for statistical analysis.

		Cognitive	Grandiosity
Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.164
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.04
	N	112	112
Grandiosity	Pearson Correlation	-0.164	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.04	
	N	112	112

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between Cognitive Empathy and Grandiosity. There was a weak, negative correlation between Cognitive Empathy and Grandiosity, which was statistically significant ($r = -0.164$, $n = 112$, $p = .04$)(10).

		Grandiosity	Affective
Grandiosity	Pearson Correlation	1	0.064
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.505
	N	112	112
Affective	Pearson Correlation	0.064	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.505	
	N	112	112

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between Affective Empathy and Grandiosity. There was a weak, positive correlation between Affective Empathy and Grandiosity, which was not statistically significant ($r = 0.064$, $n = 112$, $p = .505$)

Correlations			
		Cognitive	Vulnerability
Cognitive	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.176
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.03
	N	112	112
Vulnerability	Pearson Correlation	-0.176	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.03	
	N	112	112

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between Cognitive Empathy and Vulnerability. There was a weak, negative correlation between Cognitive Empathy and Vulnerability, which was statistically significant ($r = -0.176$, $n = 112$, $p = .03$)(10).

		Vulnerability	Affective
Vulnerability	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.109
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.251
	N	112	112
Affective	Pearson Correlation	-0.109	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.251	
	N	112	112

A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between Affective Empathy and Vulnerability. There was a weak, negative correlation between Affective Empathy and Vulnerability, which was not statistically significant ($r = -0.109$, $n = 112$, $p = .251$).

Discussion

The present study investigated the prevalence of pathological narcissism, cognitive empathy and affective empathy among medical professionals across various departments. [3] The results showed a significant prevalence of pathological narcissism with the highest rates found in the surgical fraternities and the lowest in psychiatry (17%) and pathology (18%). These findings are consistent with previous research suggesting that surgeons tend to score higher on narcissistic personality traits [4].

In contrast, cognitive empathy was found to be high across most departments, with the exception of obstetrics and gynaecology (33%). Affective empathy also showed a similar trend. These findings support the idea that medical professionals in general tend to possess high levels of empathy [5].

The correlation analysis revealed a weak negative correlation between cognitive empathy and grandiosity, suggesting that individuals with higher cognitive empathy tend to have lower levels of grandiosity. Similarly, a weak negative correlation was found between cognitive empathy and vulnerability, indicating that individuals with higher cognitive empathy tend to be less vulnerable. These findings support the idea that empathy and narcissism are inversely related [6].

Previous studies have explored the association between narcissism and empathy in medical

students, yielding mixed results. A study by Miles et al. [7] found a negative correlation between narcissistic personality traits and empathy in medical students, suggesting that individuals with higher levels of narcissism tend to have lower level of empathy(5). Similarly, a study by Youssef et al. (2020) found that medical students with higher levels of narcissism were less likely to engage in empathetic behaviours [8]. However a study by Hojatet al.(2015) found no significant correlation between narcissism and empathy in medical students [3]. A systematic review by Reniers et al.(2012) found that the correlation between narcissism and empathy varied across studies, ranging from -0.23 to 0.15 [7]. Overall, the evidence suggests that there may be a negative correlation between narcissism and empathy in medical students, but further research is needed to confirm this association. [9-13]

Limitations: The study had a small sample size and was conducted in a single institution, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future studies should aim to recruit a larger sample size and include multiple institutions to confirm the results.

Conclusion

This study investigated the prevalence of pathological narcissism, cognitive empathy, and affective empathy among medical professionals across various departments. The results showed a significant prevalence of pathological narcissism, particularly in the surgical fraternities, and a high level of cognitive empathy across most departments. Affective empathy was also found almost same as the cognitive empathy across all departments.

The correlation analysis revealed a negative relationship between cognitive empathy and grandiosity, suggesting that individuals with higher cognitive empathy tend to have lower levels of narcissistic tendencies. Similarly, a negative correlation was found between cognitive empathy and vulnerability, indicating that individuals with higher cognitive empathy tend to be less vulnerable.

The findings of these study highlights the importance of empathy and narcissism in medical professionals and suggest that these traits may vary across different departments. These results have implications for medical educations and training programs, which should aim to foster empathy and reduce narcissistic tendencies in medical professionals. By promoting empathy and addressing narcissistic tendencies, medical professionals can provide better professional care and improve health outcomes.

Acknowledgement: The authors would like to thank all the seniors of psychiatry department and all the medical students who participated in this study.

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